

D4.18 Cogwheel Workshop 5

WP4 Joint integrative projects

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Report from Cogwheel Workshop 5 One Health EJP / JPIAMR

Introduction

In Work Package 4 (WP4) of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), EU initiatives that require strategic interaction with OHEJP are identified in collaboration with WP2 and WP5, to avoid redundancy and to further leverage the alignment at EU level. One of the instruments, so called cogwheel workshops (CWs), are being organised by WP4 to allow key actors and relevant partners within the OHEJP, typically Project leaders or WP leaders within Joint Research Projects (JRP:s) or Joint Integrative Projects (JIP:s), to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. Before contacting the relevant EU initiative/project, it is important to identify and collect (common) JRP and JIP needs and to define if the initiative complies with these needs. Furthermore, it is important to see if the initiative can complement or assist the OHEJP, for instance with database/repositories, protocols, advice, practical collaboration (sequencing, bioinformatics) and so on.

Eight CWs will be organised during the OHEJP. The reports from the CWs will be part of the input to the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) of WP2, as well as the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of WP7.

The target for the fifth CW was five projects funded through the 9th call from the Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance (JPIAMR) on Diagnostics and Surveillance;

- MAGITICS: MACHine learning for diGItal diagnosTICS of antimicrobial resistance; <https://www.jpiamr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/MAGITICS.pdf>
- K-STaR: A K-mer Based Approach for Institutional AMR Surveillance, Transmission Monitoring, and Rapid Diagnostics; <https://www.jpiamr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/K-STaR.pdf>
- OASIS: One Health AMR Surveillance through Innovative Sampling; <https://www.jpiamr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/OASIS.pdf>
- TRluMPH: Improving the TRicycle protocol: upscaling to national Monitoring, detection of CPE and WGS pipelines for One Health Surveillance; <https://www.jpiamr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/TRluMPH.pdf>
- IDx: An exploration of regulatory, corporate, relational, and technical barriers to uptake of diagnostics in the fight against AMR; <https://www.jpiamr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/IDx.pdf>

The CW will ensure that OHEJP development is complementary and that potential synergies are identified.

Practicalities

- Information about the upcoming cogwheel workshop was sent to all OHEJP Project leaders and deputies and members of the Scientific Steering Board (SSB) on 19 March 2020. Information about JPIAMR was included.
- Five OHEJP projects (two from the integrative category; Care and OH-Harmony Cap, and three from the foodborne zoonose category; TOXOSOURCE, MedVetKlebs and NOVA) responded and 10 out of 12 JPIAM projects in total were identified as relevant. Five of the JPIAMR projects were invited, ensuring all OHEJP projects having at least one project of interest. All five invited JPIAMR projects attended the workshop.
- Invitation to the CW was sent on 3 April 2020 with deadline for registration on 21 April 2020.
- Seven OHEJP and the five invited JPIAMR projects signed up with presentations at the CW. Twelve OHEJP projects were represented in total.
- The CW was held as an online meeting with 38 participants using Adobe Connect on 28 April 2020. The agenda is included in the annex.
- The meeting was recorded until lunch, and a document with link to the recorded meeting, the given presentations and contact information for follow-up questions was distributed one week after the CW.

Attendance list

Project	Representatives (institution)
FARMED	Manal AbuOun (APHA) Kevin Vanneste (Sciensano) Carlus Deneke (BfR)
FULL- FORCE	Pieter Jan Ceyskens (Sciensano) Henrik Hasman (SSI) Benoit Doublet (INRAE) Alma Brolund (Public Health Agency of Sweden)
LISTADAPT	Yann Sevellec (ANSES)
MATRIX	Esther Maria Sundermann (BfR)
OH-HARMONY-CAP	Nadia Boisen (also OHEJP administration, SSI)
ORION	Estíbalís López de Abuchuco (BfR)
TOXOSOURCES	Pikka Jokelainen (also OHEJP administration, SSI)
ADONIS	Ana Amaro (INIAV) Clara Samper (VISA VET-UCM) Angela Pista (INSA)
CARE	Mia Torpdahl (SSI) Mery Pina (IP)
DiSCoVeR	Vicente Lopez Chavarrias (VISA VET-UCM)
RaDar	Kyrre Kausrud (NVI) Madelaine Norström (NVI)
OHEJP Administration	Solveig Sølverød Mo (NVI) Kristin Pettersen (NVI) Marie Nykvist (SVA) Karin Artursson (SVA) María Ugarte Ruiz (VISA VET-UCM) Cécile Boland (Sciensano) Racha El Mounaged (Sciensano)
Other	Teresa Nogueira (INIAV)

Output

All OHEJP projects interested in participating in the CW had the opportunity to do so. The relevant key elements in JPIAMR, as identified by each OHEJP project, are listed below. The proposed action points from each project are listed in a separate summary table below.

Meeting summary, per project

Key elements in JPIAMR relevant for each EJP project:

<u>EJP Project</u>	<u>FARMED and APHA</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The K-STaR project seems quite appropriate for FARMED, and sharing of practical bioinformatics ideas are of interest. Also the applicability of their currently available software could be tested. Their focus seemed to be on long read sequencing of isolates / targeted metagenomics of specific species. Therefore an unbiased metagenomic approach on a complex matrix might require a different analysis approach. The machine learning in MAGITICS could be useful for FARMED also. Publication https://www.nature.com/articles/s41564-019-0656-6 and Software https://github.com/c2-d2/rase were also mentioned.
<u>EJP Project</u>	<u>FULL-FORCE</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Although there is no immediate overlap between the presented projects and FULL_FORCE, the k-mer approach pursued by K-STaR project sounds very attractive as a follow-up action after the MedVet groups have established their capacity for long-read sequencing.
<u>EJP Project</u>	<u>LISTADAPT</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No overlap with the LISTADAPT project was reported
<u>EJP Project</u>	<u>MATRIX</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surveillance in One Health was identified as relevant in general Relevant key elements in JPIAMR were knowledge, collaboration, ensuring non-overlapping activities and AMR priorities. These key elements were also relevant for ADONIS, DiSCoVeR and OH-HARMONY-CAP.
<u>EJP Project</u>	<u>OH-HARMONY-CAP</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We expect that there will be no or very little overlap between OH-Harmony-Cap and the JPIAMR projects. Notably, OH-Harmony-Cap is only focusing on zoonotic pathogens and AMR for Salmonella and Campylobacter in EU. Seeing that our aim is to harmonize protocols and propose a harmonised testing strategy for Europe, the output and deliverables will be designed in such a way that they can be used in laboratories, which might be beneficial for some JPIAMR projects. Relevant key elements as described for MATRIX
<u>EJP Project</u>	<u>ORION</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No overlap with the ORION project was identified.
<u>EJP Project</u>	<u>TOXOSOURCES</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Networking between projects
<u>EJP Project</u>	<u>ADONIS, MATRIX, MOMIR-PPC and DISCoVeR (VISA-VET-UCM)</u>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tools, omics knowledge and One Health approach (TRIuMPH) were identified as relevant key elements.

- Some of the JPIAMR projects using ‘omics’ as the main tool to study antimicrobial resistance, such as K-STaR, are very relevant to the developing work within bioinformatics in the VISAVET project.
- JPIAMR provides complementary background knowledge to DISCoVeR, which overall aims to provide the basis for future approaches for source attribution of zoonotic foodborne pathogens and AMR. Further and deeper research in these areas will bring good ideas, and hopefully, useful solutions to the challenges posed by AMR.

EJP Project	CARE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From the presentations made by the JPIAMR projects, both MAGITICS and K-STaR might be relevant for CARE. WP2 and WP3 in CARE will be working with creation of a EURO panel of One Health reference material and the access and sustainability of well defined microbial reference material. • Direct action points and collaboration is not foreseen as the projects are running simultaneously and with different target organisms; CARE focuses in a one health zoonotic perspective and MAGITICS and K-STaR is oriented around developing databases and tools for prediction of resistance emergence. 	

EJP Project	RaDAR
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The projects presented had little to no overlap with RADAR, possibly methodology used in MAGITICS could be of relevance for WP1 in RADAR. However, no participants from WP1 RADAR were present at the meeting so it’s hard to tell. • Interesting workshop and even if synergy points to current projects we are involved in not was detected, it will certainly be beneficial to have the information of the projects provided for future studies. 	

EJP Project	OHEJP WP3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking between projects 	

EJP Project	OHEJP WP5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking between projects • JPIAMR as OHEJP stakeholder – mutual added value is obvious 	

Summary table Action points

Project	Action points	Who, when
FARMED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact K-STaR group to discuss possible collaboration • Test software 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP2 leaders (Saria Otani, Kevin Vanneste, Carlus Deneke), in the next 12 months
FULL-FORCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None identified at this point 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
LISTADAPT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None identified at this point 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
MATRIX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact for collaboration, also relevant for ADONIS and DiSCoVeR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leader and Deputy Leader of each project, when relevant.
OH-HARMONY-CAP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None identified at this point 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
ORION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None identified at this point 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
TOXOSOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue following the other projects for points of shared interest/synergy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pikka Jokelainen, Continuing

ADONIS and DISCoVeR/VISAVET-UCM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Following up on omics knowledge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All partners. When was not identified.
CARE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None identified at this point 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">
RaDAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None as we only participated to get some general information of the projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">
OHEJP WP3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue following the projects for points of shared interest/synergy Follow up how participation will be reported by the JRPs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pikka Jokelainen, Continuing
OHEJP WP5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue following the projects for points of shared interest/synergy Mention/discuss this workshop at SCM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pikka Jokelainen, Continuing

Other comments

- Even though no collaboration opportunities were immediately identified for some of the projects, insight in the JPIAMR project was confirmed interesting and relevant in general for the OHEJP projects. Also, the presentations given by the OHEJP projects is a good opportunity for updates and looking for potential synergies within the OHEJP.
- JPIAMR will arrange a workshop in November on surveillance, and OHEJP was invited to initiate further collaboration.
- Some of the JPIAMR projects were in early stages, and some outside the EU, which may have challenged the identification of relevance.
- For detailed information, the presentations were not deep enough, and sharing of a document with contact information to the presenters was requested. This way, participants could contact the relevant projects directly and get more information if relevant.
- Feedback was given on the importance of also identifying projects that do not overlap, and that collaboration is not the only aim. Learning from each other is also important.
- Aspects of the JPIAMR projects covering economy was highly appreciated.
- Considering all new approaches to omics it is suggested and appreciated working together – enhancing the possibility to do “big things”.
- Participants confirmed that the format of the meeting was satisfying.
- The EU project SafeConsume was suggested by TOXOSOURCES as relevant for the CW#6

Concluding remarks

Representatives from the OHEJP were content with the cogwheel workshop. In general, no major overlaps between JPIAMR and the OHEJP projects represented were identified. The participants were happy with the online format of the meeting.

Presentations given at the meeting

See Annex.

The recording of the cogwheel workshop can be accessed through the following link; <https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/p99orsayzc7o/>